

SOCIAL FEATURES OF ENSURING GENDER EQUALITY IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *In this article, the author describes the specific aspects of the work being done to support women and create equal opportunities for women and men, which is one of the priorities of the reforms being carried out in New Uzbekistan, as well as the legal basis of such important reforms. and, of course, substantiated with facts and concrete information about the importance of such news today.*

Key words: *Development strategy of New Uzbekistan, legal reforms, domestic and social violence, Sustainable development goals, social protection, new social policy, professional and intellectual education of women, employment of young women and girls, global changes in the world.*

СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ГЕНДЕРНОГО РАВЕНСТВА В НОВОМ УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье автор описывает конкретные аспекты проводимой работы по поддержке женщин и созданию равных возможностей для женщин и мужчин, что является одним из приоритетов проводимых в Новом Узбекистане реформ, а также правовой основой таких важных реформ. и, конечно же, подкрепленные фактами и конкретной информацией о важности таких новостей сегодня.*

Ключевые слова: *Стратегия развития Нового Узбекистана, правовые реформы, домашнее и социальное насилие, Цели устойчивого развития, социальная защита, новая социальная политика, профессиональное и интеллектуальное образование женщин, занятость молодых женщин и девушек, глобальные изменения в мире.*

INTRODUCTION.

The social foundations of achieving gender equality at the new stage of development of our society, the effectiveness of gender equality in the implementation of the development strategy, the tasks of guaranteeing the rights and freedoms and status of women and thereby implementing social protection and a strong social policy are researched in this manuscript. It is also intended to consider the social foundations of achieving gender equality in society based on values, social norms and social needs.

At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, gender issues and reforms aimed at ensuring gender equality have become one of the urgent tasks. "In recent years, large-scale efforts aimed at achieving equal rights and opportunities for women and men, ensuring their equal participation in the management of society and state affairs, supporting women in social and legal terms, as well as protecting women from oppression and violence reforms"[1] are being implemented. One of the important tasks in this regard is the development of the Sustainable Development Goals and the adoption of the state program for achieving gender equality.

Today, it is becoming more evident that gender equality is of urgent importance in social relations, which are important for the development of society. Today, as a result of special attention being paid to the establishment of gender equality relations in the family and society, increasing the activity of women in social life, great changes are being made in social relations and legislation. The relationship between men and women in society is primarily determined by the characteristics of national culture and improves in accordance with changes in society and life conditions. In our country, women and men have their own place and status in social life. The opportunities given to women to realize their talents and abilities have an impact on the improvement of gender relations, as well as on the preservation of national identity, such as honoring women, respect and attention to her. Taking effective measures for the equal participation of men and women in politics, economy and society, conducting active policies will also lead to significant positive results in increasing the effectiveness of the social protection system for women.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

An in-depth analysis of the tasks defined in the strategy of the new Uzbekistan revealed the necessary need to create a completely new system based on the essence for the formation of gender equality, re-evaluation of gender relations from the point of view of human value, as well as for establishing a new attitude to the social protection of women. Deficiencies in the system were studied and measures were taken to eliminate them. The policy of dialogue with the people, which started in our country, was of particular importance in the development of mechanisms to eliminate existing system deficiencies. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, said, organizing an open, face-to-face dialogue with the people is the most important factor in determining the problems of every citizen and solving these problems in a targeted manner[2].

The social foundations of achieving gender equality in society are more evident in the attitude towards women in the social environment. That is, the social basis is closely related to social relations, and its factor indicates the importance of the issue. According to the strategy of achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, "the system of covering the tuition fees of needy girls who lost their parents or one of them, single women without a breadwinner was introduced, and the number of grants for girls from needy families for admission to higher educational institutions was doubled.

In order to support women's entrepreneurship, over 224,000 women were granted preferential loans in the amount of 6.9 trillion soums. The result of such reforms in the field had a positive effect on the place of our country in international rankings, and in the Women, Business and Law Index of the World Bank, Uzbekistan was included among the 27 countries that implemented important reforms in the field of women's rights and gender equality in 2020, and increased by 5 places, among 190 countries. took 134th place. In addition, it is planned to develop a national qualification system in order to adapt the qualifications of personnel among women to the requirements of the international labor market.

After all, the social protection of representatives of the sections in need in our country, especially women, there is a single goal, which is - to raise their standard of living, relieve them from a difficult social situation, and reduce poverty by providing them with social, economic, and spiritual support. However, despite this, there are also strategic features of social protection

of women, and this factor is particularly relevant at the new stage of the development of our country.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The social foundations of ensuring gender equality are based on the implementation of social protection and social support strategies of each country. In Uzbekistan, social protection of the population is one of the continuous priorities in the program of economic reforms, that is, it is among the tasks that are considered a priority at all stages of reforms. In our country, a completely new social policy is being conducted based on the fact that the government should serve the people, not the contrary. However, the legal environment of the social protection system with new content and new structural structures, which relies on the activation of people, the strengthening of human capital resources, and the stabilization of each person in his "I", has been created, and a legal basis has been laid for it.

The social importance of ensuring gender equality provides an opportunity to use human potential to the maximum. Therefore, in the environment of the new Uzbekistan, the support system based on the literal socialization of the market economy system, that is, the full realization of human potential, has been laid, and this process is being strengthened in every way. This creates new problems and situations. Because efforts to strengthen socialization in the society, strong efforts based on gender stereotypes cannot show their high efficiency. This increases the need to create gender equality in the context of the new development of the society and, through this, to equalize the opportunities of the representatives of the two sexes in the society, and guarantee their rights and freedoms.

At this point, it is necessary to emphasize that any country, even if it is the decision of developed countries, cannot fully solve the process of social application of people only through state support. Therefore, the process of social application of the population in the new Uzbekistan is based on three strong factors, that is, state support, society relies on the active support and development of the individual's potential for social protection. In the past, the concept of social protection was mainly limited to state support. The factor of community activity was limited to providing information about the state of need of representatives of the population in need of social protection. In the process of conducting the research in almost all regions of our country, we were convinced that if the active practical support of the society and the concept of ensuring human development does not work purposefully and purposefully, this process will not always lead to a positive result. The reduction of the level of social protection needs and the improvement of the social protection system is directly related to the formation of the concept of human development. Also, many of the problems related to gender equality depend on the social thinking of the society, enlightenment, and the attitude of men and women to learning and education. That is, the social basis of the formation of gender equality is also measured by the enlightenment of the society and the educational opportunities of men and women. After all, supporting the professional and intellectual education of girls prevents women from actively participating not only in economic, but also in social and political processes, because an educated, highly educated woman can do everything with knowledge in the family, at work, and in the life of society. , takes a conscious and active approach and participates appropriately.

The life wisdom of our people that "if you raise a boy well, you will raise a person well, if you raise a girl well, you will raise a nation well" is not said for nothing. Therefore, the main

condition for raising our children to be healthy and well-rounded people loyal to the Motherland, first of all, wide opening of scientific and professional paths for women, also serves to provide social support. As the head of our state stated, if we want to raise future Khorezms, Ferghanis, Berunis, Bukharis, Ulugbeks, Navoi, first of all, we need to raise healthy, highly educated and spiritual mothers. "For this, first of all, it is necessary to educate the new generation of educated and qualified personnel who will be proactive reformers, think strategically. That is why we started reforming all stages of education, from kindergarten to higher education. In order to increase the knowledge and level of not only young people, but also the members of our society as a whole, first of all, we need knowledge and high spirituality. Where there is no knowledge, there will be backwardness, ignorance and, of course, error.

Communicating with the people in New Uzbekistan gave an opportunity to create a completely new, innovative model of social protection of our entire society, especially women. The basis of this innovative approach is the individual, targeted study of the problems of every woman living in a difficult social situation living in our country and the full realization of the potential of each family and individual into a social movement, activation of the human factor. In this way, it imposes the tasks of eliminating gender stereotypes in society, changing attitudes towards them, and creating equal opportunities for both sexes.

Social protection of women is a system of social protection that takes into account national and cultural peculiarities on the basis of general humanitarian principles as the most priority direction of the social policy implemented in the country. It is a process of protecting the remaining women, ensuring their employment, preventing crime among them, ensuring gender equality, strengthening family values, and protecting motherhood and childhood. It can be said that in the environment of new Uzbekistan, the movement of social protection of women has essentially risen to a new level, applying an innovative approach to this issue is a social necessity of our life today. Because the progressive development of society cannot be realized without renewal and reforms, especially without innovative approaches. This situation can be explained as an objective law of social development.

Increasing the intellectual potential of the society and raising its level of enlightenment are of great importance in ensuring gender equality. Especially increasing the intellectual potential of women, sharpening their thinking, worldview, encouraging them to learn, creating opportunities for them to acquire modern specialties has a strong impact on the development of society. There is no doubt that the strengthening of the intellectual factor affects the indicators of self-evaluation of women in our country as possessors of a certain profession, craft and creative potential.

Therefore, social protection of women by strengthening the intellectual factor is an integral aspect of the innovative approach to this issue in the new Uzbekistan. In order to systematically increase the phenomenon of self-evaluation from the point of view of professional and creative potential, it is necessary for girls to have in-depth knowledge, to analyze the situation of choosing a field of professional activity that meets the requirements of today's market, to eliminate the identified problems, to realize the abilities of women, especially young girls. for them, it is necessary to develop specific proposals for the organization of associations in various areas of their interest.

DISCUSSION

Another reason for the acceleration of innovative processes in the system of social protection of women is global changes in the world - the Internet, the formation of a single economic and information space. The desire to master, use and create advanced technologies in all areas of society is, on the one hand, a result of globalization, on the other hand, is a form of striving for improvement that occurs in the process of sustainable development. The movement to create an innovative model aimed at improving the effectiveness of various systems for improving our lives, in particular, the social protection system for women, is also an example of the desire to fundamentally posit the existing situation.

In order to achieve gender equality in the new Uzbekistan, the factors affecting the improvement of the system can be classified as follows:

- first, the existing social environment in the society - the existence of conditions for social development, health care, employment, and education system are being developed;
- the second, cultural and spiritual life in society - the ability to accept and use scientific innovations is being developed in society and in the minds of its members;
- thirdly, the system of values - the high human attitude towards women, the fact that great social attention is paid to women as active subjects of knowledge, science and innovation.

The happiness of every person, his future life is inextricably linked with the fate of all mankind. The development of the current historical processes is classified, on the one hand, by the persistence of conflicts between different countries, on the other hand, by the increasing interdependence of the countries of the world community, and the internationalization of the social life and lifestyle of different peoples. At the same time, creating the material and spiritual conditions for a truly human life worthy of all nations, providing life on our planet, treating its wealth, first of all, the greatest wealth - man himself, his potential - are becoming the pressing problems of today. "Now a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inalienable rights and freedoms are considered sacred and they are guaranteed by the state." [3] One of the most important issues in this regard is inter-ethnic relations, and this issue is an important component of the national security of each country.

In the process of social and political development of the world, views were formed that men and women have equal rights, they are free to choose the type of work, think and build a family. At the heart of these views lies the noble intention of making a woman a subject of social life. A number of activities are being carried out in the world community to ensure equal rights for women with men, to expand their opportunities in social, economic, and political life, and to create equal opportunities for education. Increasing the activity of women in society is legally guaranteed in Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION

The priority tasks of creating gender equality in the new Uzbekistan and thereby bringing human dignity to a new level, maximum use of human potential, implementing social protection, and changing some rules and values in social relations in society are the following directions:

First, to increase the socio-political activity of women in Uzbekistan, to demonstrate their talents and abilities in various fields, to ensure their rights and legal interests, to implement large-scale work on strengthening the institution of the family, in particular, the control and coordination of this activity is the deputy district (city) mayor, wife - assignment to the chairpersons of the girls' committee increases their responsibilities, as well as ensuring

cooperation in issues such as preparing girls for life, preventing early marriage, ensuring family stability, and conducting wedding ceremonies in an orderly manner.

Second, a clear mechanism was created to improve the living conditions of mothers who need help and live in difficult social conditions, including disabled women, low-income women, mothers who have lost their breadwinners, and mothers raising their children alone. According to the results of this study, each family in need of assistance will be supported through "Roadmaps" developed separately at the citizens' meeting. In our country, the Public Fund for Women and Family Support, which is formed at the expense of the state budget and is directed to the implementation of clearly targeted measures for the social protection of women, has been successfully operating.

The third is to ensure women's employment, involve them in family and private entrepreneurship, train them, and improve their working conditions. This task is implemented annually on the basis of the Comprehensive Action Program adopted by the government.

The fourth is to ensure close cooperation between state bodies and civil society institutions in order to improve the moral and moral environment in the society, to prevent crimes and disorders among the population. On the basis of the fourth priority direction defined in the decree, work is being carried out to improve the moral and moral environment in households, neighborhoods, among the population, especially women and young people, and fight against crime.

The life wisdom of our people - "if you raise a boy well, you will raise a person well, if you raise a girl well, you will raise a nation well" is said with enormous meaning. Therefore, the main condition for raising our children to be healthy and well-rounded people loyal to the Motherland, first of all, wide opening of scientific and professional paths for women, also serves to provide social support. As the head of our state stated, if we want to raise future Khorezms, Ferghanis, Berunis, Bukharis, Ulugbeks, Navoi, first of all, we need to raise healthy, highly educated and spiritual mothers. For this, first of all, it is necessary to educate the new generation of educated and qualified personnel who will be proactive reformers, think strategically. That is why we started reforming all stages of education, from kindergarten to higher education. In order to increase the knowledge and level of not only young people, but also the members of our society as a whole, first of all, knowledge and high spirituality are needed. Where there is no knowledge, there will be backwardness, ignorance and, of course, mistake.

In conclusion, at the new stage of the feature of development of the society, the social bases of ensuring fairness in the formation of gender equality, equality in the relations between men and women, balance in their status and guarantee of their rights and freedoms depend on the social and gender stereotypes of the society, the strategy of social protection, as well as its beliefs, moral values and other national and cultural characteristics. originates. This increases the possibility of achieving gender equality by studying these issues in depth and researching their positive and negative aspects.

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